

The Grapes of Wrath as a Social Indictment

Shubhangi Nivrutti Lavate

Research Student, Dr. Patangrao Kadam Mahavidyalaya, Ramanandnagar (Burli) 416308 Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author E-mail: lavateatharv3@gmail.com

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Abstract

The Grapes of Wrath is certainly John Steinbeck's most celebrated work. It is an artistic portrayal of the plight of the agricultural tenants during the Great Depression of the Thirties. Indeed, it is a sensitive work of art. The description of the journey of the Joads alternates with a running commentary on the plight of the refugees or migrants as a pass. The Joads are character types. They suffer from a prolonged drought in the rural areas of the central prairie. This is coupled with acute unemployment in the urban areas and the growing menaces of soulless industrialization. Hence, The Grapes of Wrath is structured at many levels and generates currents of meaning from them all. Steinbeck himself was one of the victims of the Depression and the novel embodies his immediate reaction of wrath and defiance suffused with pity and compassion.

Keywords: Wrath, Oklahoma, Agricultural Tenants, Depression of the Thirties, draught, Starvation, migrant, compassion, etc.

The Grapes of Wrath is a story of compassion and it is also a story of pity or mingled with wrath. Compassion is for the underdog or the poor tenant farmers and wrath for a soulless economic system that makes such tragedies possible. Thus, The Grapes of Wrath portrays with great sensitiveness a farming family's battle with starvation and the economic depression of the thirties. It is a vivid narration of a prodigious trek of the Joads from the Dust Bowl of Oklahoma to the promised land of California, only to find themselves ruthlessly exploited and reduced to near starvation. The story is rooted in history and Steinbeck himself had accompanied some labourers to the west. The migrant fruit pickers are harassed by the police and are plundered by death. The alternate chapters of the novel set their story in perspective by tracing the experiences of the migrant community as a whole. Thus, Steinbeck's approach is at once biological, political, and social. He starts with an account of the unbalanced relationship between man and nature that has produced the Dust Bowl. Then he proceeds to describe how the unfortunate share-cropping Oakies fall victim to the profit system. The eviction cannot be found in one source. It is the banks that own the land that are responsible for the tragedy. The banks want to earn profit. A bank has its own its own laws of functioning. The group overrides the individual. The banks decide that the time has come to mechanise agriculture. Overnight, the bulldozers

demolish holdings and cabins that represent so many years of labour and hope. Like their pioneering ancestors these displaced citizens have to set out on the migrant trail to the west. A sincere reader would know that Steinbeck's narration of this crisis has a quasi-biological objectivity but also in itself constitutes a criticism of the American way of life.

The Joad family is a symbol of urge of life to go on at all costs. Through all their increasing misfortunes they hold on to one another like the units of an organism and fight with other organisms like the state and the capitalist industry for their bare survival. The collective resilience and durability of the Joads is an objective study of group behaviour. There is political strain, the passage dealing with the machinations of the Californian employers who try to attract a pool of reserve labourers by deliberate publicity and then cut wages ruthlessly to near the breadline. Equally horrifying is the political chicanery resulting in fruit being coated with tar and thrown into the sea to maintain scarcity and keep the prices up.

Introductory panels, through which Dos Passos sought to present the background against which the story is written, are there. Passages are there in the introspective technique of Joyce; others reminding of the curt understatement of Hemingway; others which echo the diapaean rhetoric of Thomas Wolfe. But at the same time there are stretches of narrative which might have come out of *Gone with the Wind*, or a serial in *Saturday Evening Post*. (p.113)

The socio-economic conditions of the migrants in the Depression of the Thirties were pitiable. The banks which own the land that the sharecroppers occupy decide that they must cut their losses. They go in for mechanized agriculture. The tenants are given quit notice. The bulldozers demolish overnight the small holdings and cabins that represent so many years of hope and labour. The tractors come ploughing up huge tracts of land for cotton cultivation. Some of the tenants try to argue with them but the corporations have no personality of their own. The driver of the bulldozer may be Joe Devis' boy but he is working for three dollars only a day. Deputies scour the land to see that no evicted tenant lingers on. Joads sell all their belongings, invest half their savings in second-hand cars or trucks and start hopefully on a two-thousand-mile odyssey to the promised land of California.

Again, the roads are flooded with families in flight. They are helpless refugees from dust and shrinking land, from the thunder of tractors and shrinking ownership. They have been lured by orange-coloured hand-bills and call for thousands of workers on good wages to pick oranges and apples, peaches and cotton. This seething mass of humanity rides the waves of hope and are reaching out to what they think a land flowing with milk and honey. But the road to California is littered with frustration. America, they say, is the land of freedom but these refugees discover with painful surprise that they are just as free as they have got money to pay for it. It is only the dollar that talks and no human misery. Further the Joads see families returning from California with bitter things to say about the unemployment there. The picture these returning men paint is so grim that some like Noah, consider it discreet to slip away. The Okies who had hoped to find a home only find hatred. The owners hate them because they threaten to swarm their property. The store-keepers hate them because they have no money to spend. The bankers hate them because there is nothing to gain from them. The labouring natives hate them because the Okies by their fierce eagerness to work just to eat are reducing their wages to starvation level. The homeless Okies cannot understand why the Californians are so unreasonable. To those hungry folk, an empty field (ploughed but not used field) is a sin and unused land a crime against the thin children. Homervilles arise all over the place. The natives, either by themselves in gangs or with the help of deputies, burn out these warts on their security. But then the burnings, the arrests and the killings do not succeed in stopping the onrush of wave of the hardened, homeless dispossessed. They step up mechanization, throw more families on the road, form associations for protection and spend money on arms, or gas to protect the great holdings, on spies to catch the murmuring of revolt, on deputies to deal with the trouble-makers under the pretence of law and on hiring hooligans who will sniff out the leaders of revolt.

Grapes of Wrath does not conclude on a sour note, but rather on a positive note, with the promise of a brighter future. It guarantees that progress is made despite setbacks. Rose of Sharon loses her husband and kid but yet does something noble. During the floodwaters, the Joads find a barn to refuge in. They see a hungry

father and a worried son inside. To keep his son alive, the father has given up all of his meals, but he is now in danger of dying. Rose of Sharon saves the guy who was about to die by sharing her breast milk with him. e Joads' family, which was larger at the start of their voyage to California, grows smaller as the narrative progresses. Grandpa and grandma pass away as a result of old age and travel. Three of the family's young men forsake the others in the middle of their trek. Tom hides in fear of the police after killing a guy in retaliation for Casy's murder. Connie abandons his pregnant wife to pursue his job. Noah abandons his family and vanishes in Oklahoma. Only the ladies survive, and they inspire confidence in the other guys in the household. Perry D. West Brook has very rightly observed that the westward journey of the Joad is symbolic of their rebirth. West Brook agrees with □oreau that "We go east-ward to realize history and study the works of art and literature, retracing the steps of the race; we go westward as into the future, with a spirit of enterprise and adventure" (p.215).

The trick these people play is to advertise for ten times the number of hands they actually require. If they want eight hundred hands they will call for eight-thousand; and twenty thousand will actually apply. When competition is so severe, it is easy to cut down the wages from thirty cents an hour to twenty or twenty-five cents. A single man like Jim Casey may fight for fair wages but men with wives and children are thankful for any crumb from the table. The breaking of the strike at the Hooper Ranch is a cruel instance in point.

There is even a more satanic aspect to this muddle. The Californian valley is fertile. The land quickens the produce the fruits grow heavy, scientists give of their best to increase and improve the yield. But there is no money in the hands of the people to buy the fruits or alcohol. The big owners start canning of the fruits, but the men who have created these fruits cannot create a system by which their fruits may be eaten. So decay spreads over the land. Carloads of oranges and a million hungry people needing the oranges cannot take them. Coffee is burnt in the ships for fuel. Potatoes are dumped in the rivers. Pigs are slaughtered and buried and the smell infects all the countryside. This is a crime that goes beyond denunciation. It is a sorrow that weeping cannot symbolize. The earth is fertile and rich with fruit, but children die of Pallgra and women deliver dead babies due to malnutrition. In the eyes of the people, the grapes of wrath are filling and growing heavy, growing heavy for the vintage.

The homeless, jobless millions crawl from pillar to post with hunger and anger in their sunken eyes. At every step and everywhere there is the climax of the suffering and humiliation. Yet the Joads refuse to be broken. It is the mark of mankind to be tough. The Joad family is defeated but still is resolute. The urge of life to continue through every kind of vicissitude has been prefigured by the famous early chapters delineating the progress of the land turtle. As Ma epitomises it, "us people can go on living, when all them people is gone." Man lives by hope. Even in the darkness or in the darkest gloom there is a distant glimmer of hope, beckoning him to. Again in Ma's words, "We keep a-comin. You fret none, less Tom. A different time's comin."

The Joad family has lost everything but love is not lost, because it is not outside. It is essentially in the hearts of the men. The river of springs from within. Against the bleak backdrop of rains, hunger and complete ruination. Ma Joad's love and her limitless compassion guide her daughter. Rose of Sharon, to make the great gesture, a gesture charged with divine violence of the resurrection and the life. It is a gesture that splendoursly redeems the climate scene. This is the truth for which Jim Casy, who founded Orthodox Christianity unsatisfactory died, "May be all men get one big soul everybody is a part." It is this basic reality of the human situation that "The Grapes of Wrath" tries to stress in wrath and compassion.

By any standard, "The Grapes of Wrath" is a folk epic, incarnating as it does with controlled tension the anger and compassion which Steinbeck saw the spectacle of the wriggles and means of humanity. Perhaps, "The Grapes of Wrath is the only American proletarian fiction of the Thirties. Though it is proletarian in its theme Steinbeck is by no means of absorbing interest with a vivid description.

Conclusion

The above discussion clearly shows that "The Grapes of Wrath" stands as a social indictment. It also stands as a haunting image of the great depression of the 1930s. Indeed, it is the story of wrath and compassion

stressed with power and grace. It portrays with great sensitiveness a farming family's battle with starvation and the economic depression of the Thirties. Joads' family learns to collaborate with strangers and to be empathetic and adaptable on campus as a result of their move from Oklahoma to California. Despite the rude treatment they have received, they continue to serve others and remain united. In *The Grapes of Wrath* (1939), Steinbeck emphasizes the significance of staying unified to survive in difficult times. *The Grapes of Wrath* brilliantly captures the farmers' anguish, aspirations for a better life, and unfulfilled promises (1939). He adds a dramatic element to the narrative as well as a personal touch. With his great personality, he raises the whole human race.

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